

Kindness Love Satisfaction Peace Excellence Money Happiness Respect Intelligence Health Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (KLSPEMHRIHAIA)

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Abstract—Kindness Love Satisfaction Peace Excellence Money Happiness Respect Intelligence Health Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (KLSPEMHRIHAIA) is the novel and unique algorithm invented in this article. This algorithm belongs to Human Swarm Optimization (HSO) field.

Keywords—Human Swarm Optimization, HSO, Swarm Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, Kindness, Love, Satisfaction, Peace, Excellence, Money, Happiness, Respect, Intelligence, Health, KLSPEMHRIHAIA

I. INTRODUCTION

Relevant Artificial intelligence literature is shown in articles [1] to [5]. An interesting algorithm titled Kindness Love Satisfaction Peace Excellence Money Happiness Respect Intelligence Health Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (KLSPEMHRIHAIA) is designed in this article. Invented KLSPEMHRIHAIA algorithm is explained in Section 2. Section 3 shows the Conclusions made. References are available at the end.

II. KINDNESS LOVE SATISFACTION PEACE EXCELLENCE MONEY HAPPINESS RESPECT INTELLIGENCE HEALTH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ALGORITHM

Ten different Arrays are initialized in lines [1] to [10]. Generation is set to 0. Best Humans are identified in lines 12 to 21. In line no. 22 for each Human loop is started. Human moves along 10 different Directions as shown in lines 23 to 32. Unit Vectors of all directions are obtained in line no. 33. Line no. 34 shows position update equation. Human moves along the combination of ten Directions as shown in position update equation. For each Human loop is ended in line no. 35. Generation count is incremented by 1. Lines 37 to 46 updates all the ten different arrays. This process continues until termination condition is reached in line no. 47.

Procedure: Kindness Love Satisfaction Peace Excellence Money Happiness Respect Intelligence Health Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (KLSPEMHRIHAIA)

- 1) Initialize Kindness_Array
- 2) Initialize Love_Array
- 3) Initialize Satisfaction_Array
- 4) Initialize Peace_Array
- 5) Initialize Excellence_Array
- 6) Initialize Money_Array
- 7) Initialize Happiness_Array
- 8) Initialize Respect_Array
- 9) Initialize Intelligence_Array
- 10) Initialize Health_Array

- 11) Generation = 0
- 12) Best_Kindness_Human = Human with best Kindness value
- 13) Best_Love_Human = Human with best Love value
- 14) Best_Satisfaction_Human = Human with best Satisfaction value
- 15) Best_Peace_Human = Human with best Peace value
- 16) Best_Excellence_Human = Human with best Excellence value
- 17) Best_Money_Human = Human with best Money value
- 18) Best_Happiness_Human = Human with best Happiness value
- 19) Best_Respect_Human = Human with best Respect value
- 20) Best_Intelligence_Human = Human with best Intelligence value
- 21) Best_Health_Human = Human with best Health value
- 22) for each Human:
- 23) Direction1 = Best_Kindness_Human – Human
- 24) Direction2 = Best_Love_Human – Human
- 25) Direction3 = Best_Satisfaction_Human – Human
- 26) Direction4 = Best_Peace_Human – Human
- 27) Direction5 = Best_Excellence_Human – Human
- 28) Direction6 = Best_Money_Human – Human
- 29) Direction7 = Best_Happiness_Human – Human
- 30) Direction8 = Best_Respect_Human – Human
- 31) Direction9 = Best_Intelligence_Human – Human
- 32) Direction10 = Best_Health_Human – Human
- 33) Convert all 10 Directions into unit Vectors
- 34) position = position +
0.1*Direction1*Step +
0.1*Direction2*Step +
0.1*Direction3*Step +
0.1*Direction4*Step +
0.1*Direction5*Step +
0.1*Direction6*Step +
0.1*Direction7*Step +
0.1*Direction8*Step +
0.1*Direction9*Step +
0.1*Direction10*Step
- 35) end for each Human loop
- 36) Generation = Generation + 1
- 37) Update Kindness_Array
- 38) Update Love_Array
- 39) Update Satisfaction_Array
- 40) Update Peace_Array
- 41) Update Excellence_Array
- 42) Update Money_Array
- 43) Update Happiness_Array
- 44) Update Respect_Array

- 45) Update Intelligence_Array
- 46) Update Health_Array
- 47) Loop until termination condition reached is True

III. CONCLUSIONS

An innovative algorithm titled KLSPEMHRHAIA algorithm which is based on Kindness, Love, Satisfaction, Peace, Excellence, Money, Happiness, Respect, Intelligence, Health is designed in this article. In this algorithm Human moves along the combination of ten different directions. This is just the beginning of KLSPEMHRHAIA algorithm. Many unique and novel algorithms may be invented by taking inspiration from KLSPEMHRHAIA algorithm designed in this article.

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